

Tertiary Education in the Global Innovation Index

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Tertiary education in the context of the Global Innovation Index represents a crucial indicator for measuring the quality and accessibility of higher education, a fundamental element for fostering innovation and economic growth. It encompasses universities, technical institutes, and other forms of post-secondary education that provide advanced knowledge and specialized skills. This indicator analyzes aspects such as enrollment rates in higher education, the quality of academic institutions, and international student mobility, offering a picture of a country's ability to develop a skilled workforce ready to contribute to research and development. A robust tertiary education system stimulates talent creation, promotes scientific research, and supports the dissemination of knowledge through collaborations with industry and other sectors. In innovation-leading countries, tertiary education plays a key role in attracting foreign investment and strengthening the innovation ecosystem. Conversely, lack of access or low quality in higher education can limit opportunities for technological and entrepreneurial development. In the Global Innovation Index, this indicator helps assess the competitiveness of countries, as a population with advanced tertiary education is often correlated with greater capacity to innovate and compete globally.

Tertiary Education in the Global Innovation Index 2022. The data from the 2022 Global Innovation Index regarding tertiary education highlights significant disparities among countries in terms of access and quality of higher education. Tertiary education plays a crucial role in developing the innovation ecosystem by training qualified professionals and promoting research and development activities. The results reveal a stark divide between nations with strong educational systems and those lagging behind, reflecting differences in resources, infrastructure, and policy priorities. The United Arab Emirates leads the ranking with a score of 71.5, demonstrating significant investments in higher education and success in creating a knowledge-based economy. Countries such as Singapore (66.3) and Australia (58.8) follow with high scores, thanks to world-class universities and strategies aimed at attracting international students. Austria (58.5) and Peru (57.2) also perform well, indicating well-developed tertiary education systems aligned with the needs of innovation-oriented economies. Some European countries, such as Germany (54.7), Finland (48.5), and Switzerland (47.2), maintain prominent positions due to their long-standing tradition of educational and research excellence. However, some high-income nations, like the United Kingdom (49.7) and the United States (34.9), perform below expectations, indicating potential gaps in their higher education policies. Emerging economies like Malaysia (48.7) and Qatar (50.3) are making notable progress in tertiary education, reflecting deliberate strategies to improve educational standards and broaden access. However, countries like China (19.4) and India (33.3), despite being global leaders in other innovation sectors, show moderate scores, suggesting a gap between the scale of their education systems and the quality of outcomes. The lowest positions in the ranking are dominated by low-income and developing countries, many of which face critical challenges in expanding and improving access to higher education. For instance, Sub-Saharan African nations like Kenya (3.7), Uganda (14.6), and Ghana (10.7) score low, reflecting systemic issues such as inadequate funding, insufficient infrastructure, and limited opportunities for advanced education. The lowest scores, at zero, are recorded in countries like Iraq, Zambia, and Paraguay, highlighting either a complete lack of data or significant barriers to access. The data underscores the crucial role of investments and public policies in promoting an effective tertiary education sector. Countries with higher scores tend to allocate significant resources to education, promote research, and encourage collaboration between universities and industry. In contrast, nations with weaker systems often face budgetary constraints, political instability, or the absence of strategic initiatives to strengthen their educational institutions. In conclusion, the 2022 data on tertiary education in the Global Innovation Index reveals a global landscape marked by profound inequalities. While some nations leverage their educational systems to drive innovation and

competitiveness, others face persistent challenges that limit their ability to contribute to the global knowledge economy. Addressing these disparities will require targeted investments, international cooperation, and structural reforms to ensure that all countries can benefit from the transformative power of higher education.

Tertiary Education in the Global Innovation Index Between 2013 and 2022. The data on tertiary education in the Global Innovation Index between 2013 and 2022 reveal significant variability in country performance, with some nations achieving remarkable progress while others experienced substantial declines. These changes reflect not only the political and economic priorities of each country but also their ability to adapt to the evolving demands of a global landscape. Among the countries with the most significant percentage improvements, South Africa stands out with an incredible increase of 2833.33%, rising from a score of 0.6 to 17.6. This progress highlights a greater focus on expanding access to higher education and improving its infrastructure. India, with a growth of 412.31%, has also made significant strides, cementing its role as a global hub for education and innovation. Emerging economies like Peru (+143.40%), Cambodia (+140.18%), and Canada (+138.92%) demonstrate how strategic investment in tertiary education can lead to substantial outcomes, strengthening competitiveness and innovation. However, not all countries have seen progress. Many advanced and developing economies have suffered severe setbacks. Iceland, for instance, recorded a decline of 37.7%, while countries such as Japan (-30.86%), Israel (-38.82%), and Singapore (-18.55%) experienced significant reductions. These declines can be attributed to a combination of factors, including shifts in public spending priorities, demographic decline, or reduced quality and access to higher education. Particularly concerning are the results in low-income countries, where access to tertiary education is already limited. Countries such as Mozambique (-84.93%), Guinea (-82.54%), and Sri Lanka (-69.63%) experienced dramatic declines, indicating a deterioration in educational infrastructure and opportunities for younger generations. These outcomes underscore the risk of a widening global educational gap, which could hinder these nations' ability to actively participate in the knowledge economy. Europe also showed mixed results. While some countries, like Germany (+46.65%) and Romania (+25.41%), improved their scores, others, such as Italy (-12.91%), Spain (-13.30%), and Belgium (-10.10%), experienced declines. These figures suggest that although Europe as a whole maintains a strong educational tradition, not all countries are keeping pace with the increasing demands for innovation and advanced skills.

Conclusions. The average value of tertiary education for the countries considered decreased by 3.41% during the period from 2013 to 2022, dropping from 31.04 units to 29.97 units. The top-performing countries in terms of tertiary education improvements during the 2013–2022 period include South Africa, which achieved an astounding growth of 2833.33%, followed by India with a 412.31% increase. Peru, Cambodia, and Canada also showed significant progress, recording improvements of 143.40%, 140.18%, and 138.92%, respectively. On the other hand, the worst-performing nations experienced severe declines. Mozambique registered the steepest drop at -84.93%, followed by Guinea at -82.54%, Guatemala at -75.00%, Mali at -73.77%, and Tanzania at -73.47%. These contrasting results underscore the diverse trajectories of countries in addressing challenges and leveraging opportunities in their tertiary education systems.

Performers	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	South Africa	0,6	17,6	17	2833,33
	India	6,5	33,3	26,8	412,31
	Peru	23,5	57,2	33,7	143,40
	Cambodia	11,2	26,9	15,7	140,18
	Canada	20,3	48,5	28,2	138,92
Worse Performers	Tanzania	4,9	1,3	-3,6	-73,47
	Mali	6,1	1,6	-4,5	-73,77
	Guatemala	18,4	4,6	-13,8	-75,00
	Guinea	12,6	2,2	-10,4	-82,54
	Mozambique	7,3	1,1	-6,2	-84,93

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